

Transformation of Pressure and Lorentz Boosted Temperature

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There are a number of prescriptions for a Lorentz boosted temperature. The Planck view suggests that: $T_{\text{new}} = T_{\text{old}}/g(v)$ where $g(v)=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$, the Ott view, that $T_{\text{new}} = T_{\text{old}} g(v)$ and the Landberg view that $T_{\text{new}} = T_{\text{old}}$. A Cavallieri view suggests that one can only measure temperature in the rest frame. (These views are described in detail in (1).)

Here we consider the ideal gas law $PV=nRT$ and note that the various views consider that P (Lorentz boost) = P rest frame (1). This, we suggest, means that one measures pressure from a position on the moving wall (even as seen by a person watching the moving gas). If this is the case, we argue that all measurements are made from the moving wall (i.e. T and V as well) and the person watching the moving gas may only note that overall energy transforms as rest mass $g(v)$. Thus, one may not measure $P'=P$ from the moving wall and then measure V' from the frame of someone watching the moving gas. This is inconsistent (but lead to the Planck result for T' .)

In other words, we suggest that T is like rest mass. It should be measured in a non-boosted frame. It is, however, associated with energy kT , but if viewed in motion, this energy is $kT g(v)$. For example a change in energy TdS (with S invariant) is $g(v) T dS$ from the point of view of someone watching the moving gas.

Thus, temperature only makes sense in the rest frame, but given a rest frame temperature T , a moving gas with temperature T is somewhat like a rest frame temperature of $g(v) T$ (except that the energy is associated with one directional motion). We argue this because one frequently sees the condition for a T which may produce electron-positron pairs, i.e. $2m_0 cc = kT$. If a person in a moving gas observes the production of electron-positron pairs at a minimum T , then the person in the frame watching the moving gas knows that the electron and positron are both moving and so have extra energy which is like a $T g(v)$ temperature. Temperature energy, however, should not have a directional bias, but $Tg(v)$ does, so it does not really mean that temperature has changed, but that there is extra energy because T is a rest frame concept. This is like m_0cc receiving extra directional energy in $m_0cc g(v)$.

Views of Lorentz Boosted Temperature

The Planck view on a Lorentz boosted temperature T uses (1):

$$S' = S, \quad P'=P \quad \text{and} \quad T' = T/g(v) \quad ((1))$$

In other words, entropy S and pressure P are invariants, but temperature is not.

In order to analyze this, we consider the ideal gas law $PV = nRT$ which may be used in the rest frame. (This holds even for a Juttner distribution (3).)

For someone watching the gas move, the walls also move, i.e. the whole system moves to the right at speed v_1 (as an example). To compute pressure, it seems that one should sit on the moving wall and make measurements from it. If this is the case, then all measurements should

be made from the moving wall, but this yields results for a stationary box of gas. Thus, one cannot say:

$$PV=nRT \quad \text{and} \quad P'=P \quad \text{and} \quad V'=V/g \quad (\text{Lorentz contraction}) \quad \text{to argue that} \quad T_{\text{boost}} = T_{\text{non-boost}}/g(v) \quad ((3))$$

We suggest that T is like rest mass, it is a measure made in the rest frame (in keeping with the statements of Landsberg and Cavallieri et al)(1).

The rest mass energy $m_0 c^2$, however, is not the energy when the object moves. The energy is then: $m_0 c^2 \gamma(v)$. We argue that the same condition holds for a moving gas at temperature T . Thus, there is more energy associated with a moving gas and this can be associated with a new kind of temperature $\gamma(v)T$. This is not thermal energy, however, but extra energy due to motion so it is not really temperature which has changed (just like the parameter rest mass does to change, but its associated energy does due to one-directional motion).

If one considers a gas at a very low temperature in a rest frame, then:

$$\text{Energy approx} = N m_0 c^2 + N 1.5 kT \quad ((4))$$

$$\text{This Lorentz transforms to:} \quad N m_0 c^2 \gamma(v) = N 1.5 k T \gamma(v) \quad ((5))$$

One may argue that this is similar to a gas at rest with a temperature $T \gamma(v)$. One may ask: Why would one even consider the temperature as seen from a frame watching the moving gas? We argue that there should be a physical reason and that this reason may be linked to pair production.

If one has a gas at rest at temperature T , then a standard question (2) is: What minimum temperature is needed to create electron-positron pairs?

$$\text{The solution given is:} \quad kT = 2 m_0 c^2 \quad \text{where } m_0 \text{ is the electron rest mass.} \quad ((6))$$

(See (2) for calculations.)

If a person sitting in a gas moving at speed v in the x direction notes that the threshold temperature is T for creating electrons and positrons, then the person in the frame watching the moving gas needs to realize that this is like having a rest gas with $T \gamma(v)$ because not only do the positron and electron need to be created, but they both need to move in the x direction and this involves extra energy. This extra energy is not really temperature energy because it is associated with motion in one direction, whereas temperature energy should not have a preferred direction.

First Law of Thermodynamics

The first law of thermodynamics is often presented as:

$$dE = TdS - PdV \quad ((7))$$

If pressure is measured from the moving (boosted) wall, then energy and entropy are as well. Thus, this equation is used in the gas rest frame, but dE in this frame is equivalent to $g(v) dE$ from the point of view of someone in a frame watching the moving gas. The same arguments apply to TdS and PdV , because both are energies. Given that S is a Lorentz invariant (1), $T dS$ represents the energy $g(v)TdS$. PdV is also like energy and so is seen as $PdV g(v)$.

One, however, cannot jump to conclusions and argue that if $P'=P$, then Length (rest frame) $g(v)$ = length as seen from person watching the moving gas, because Lorentz construction states that: L (watching the moving object) = L_0 (in the rest frame) $\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$. $P'=P$ means that all measurements are made from the boosted wall, i.e. in the rest frame. One cannot measure P' from one position (sitting on the moving wall) and L' from watching a moving gas.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that there has been much interest in dealing with Lorentz boosted temperature. We consider the ideal gas law $PV=nRT$ in the frame of a gas at rest. What pressure does a person see in a frame watching the gas move at velocity v_1 in the x direction? We argue that the pressure measurement should be made by someone sitting on the moving wall. This, however, means that all measurements must be made by this same person, i.e. V and T . One cannot have a person sitting on the moving wall measure P and someone else in the frame watching the moving gas measure V . This is inconsistent, but leads to T (watching boosted gas) = T rest frame / $g(v)$, i.e. the Planck result.

Like Landsberg and Cavallieri (1), it seems that T is a measurement made in a rest frame. T is a quantity like m_0 , rest mass. That is not to say, however, that energy does not boost. $m_0 \rightarrow m_0 g(v)$ and if one had a very cold gas with thermal energy $1.5 nRT$ this energy also boosts as $1.5nRT g(v)$. We argue that this is of physical significance because a person in the rest frame of a gas with temperature T may report that positron and electrons are just being formed (at this T). A person in a frame watching the moving gas would realize that even though T does not formally change (it is like m_0), energy does. If a positron and electron are created in a moving gas, they too move with v_1 and so have extra energy. Given that $2 m_0 c^2 = kT$ is used to find the temperature at which positron-electron pairs are created, then a temperature T for a moving gas is like a stationary gas with temperature $kT g(v)$ in order that there is enough energy for the positron and electron to move. This extra energy, however, is not really thermal energy because it is one directional, nevertheless the Ott notion of $g(v) kT$ is also useful under certain contexts, we argue. Similarly, TdS is measured in the rest frame and S is invariant, but TdS represents an energy and this energy value is $TdS g(v)$ as seen by someone in a frame watching the moving object. A similar conclusion holds for PdV .

References

1. Farias, Christian and Pinto, V and Moya, P. What is the Temperature of a Moving Body? Nature Reports 7 Article No. 17657 (2017)

<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-017-17526-4#:~:text=It%20is%20important%20t%20note,due%20to%20its%20statistical%20definition.>

2. U. of Texas Austin

http://www.as.utexas.edu/astronomy/education/spring98/evans_hmwk3a.pdf

3. Ranchi, John R. Comparative Analysis of Jüttner's Calculation of the Energy of a Relativistic Ideal Gas and Implications for Accelerator Physics and Cosmology

Entropy **2017**, *19*(7), 374; <https://doi.org/10.3390/e19070374>

<https://www.mdpi.com/1099-4300/19/7/374>

4. Mares, J.J. et al. Relativistic Transformation of Temperature and Mosengeil-Ott antimony Institute of Physics ASCR, Prague, Czech (2008 or later)

<https://arxiv.org/pdf/1606.02127.pdf>